

Heptazoline, a New Carbazole Alkaloid from *Clausena heptaphylla* Wt. & Arn^{1,2}

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In continuation of our studies on the carbazoles of Rutaceae³, we now report the structure of a new carbazole alkaloid heptazoline from the stem bark of *Clausena heptaphylla* Wt and Arn. ((Fam. Rutaceae; sub. Fam. Aurantiae).

Heptazoline*, C₁₈H₁₇NO₃ (I) (M⁺ 295), m.p. 212-14° is an optically inactive homogeneous (t.l.c. and mass spectrum), phenolic compound which gave a 2 : 4 DNPH derivative, m.p. 280-85° and reduced ammoniacal silver nitrate solution and showed the presence of an aldehyde function in it. The i.r. spectrum of heptazoline (ν_{max}^{Nujol} 3450, 3150, 1623, 1580, 1500 cm⁻¹) showed the presence of -NH- function, chelated hydroxyl, chelated aldehyde function and substituted aromatic system. The uv. absorption spectrum ($\lambda_{max}^{ethanol}$ 240, 275, 298 m μ with log ϵ 4.58, 4.62 and 4.40 respectively) showed the presence of 3-formyl carbazole chromophore in it⁴. Isolation of carbazole, m.p. 225° by zinc dust distillation of heptazoline confirms its carbazole skeleton.

The N.M.R. spectrum shows that (I) has two phenolic hydroxyls (δ 9.82 and 11.5; disappears on deuterations), one -NH- proton (δ 11.25, disappears on deuteration) and one aldehydic proton (δ 9.91). The three-proton singlets at δ 1.65 and 1.81, doublet for two benzylic methylene protons at δ 3.63 for 2 hydrogens (J = 10 c.p.s.) together with the vinylic multiplet for one proton at δ 5.3 show the presence of a γ : γ dimethyl allyl residue substituted on the carbazole nucleus. The signal for proton at position 4 of the carbazole nucleus⁵ is deshielded⁶ (δ 8.28) due to the proximity of the formyl group at position 3 and appears as a singlet due to absence of proton at 2 position. The proton at position 5 (δ 7.5) is ortho and meta coupled (mainly as a doublet, J = 8 c.p.s. which are further split J = 2 c.p.s.). On cyclisation with polyphosphoric acid heptazoline furnishes cycloheptazoline,

* Satisfactory analyses of compounds reported with molecular formula were obtained. DMSO was used as a solvent for all the N.M.R. spectra reported here.

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$C_{18}H_{17}NO_3$ (II), m.p. 290° (decomp.). In the N.M.R. spectrum of (II) the signals for the $\gamma : \gamma$ dimethyl allyl residue are replaced by two symmetrical triplets for 3 protons each (δ 3.03 and δ 1.98) and a singlet for 6 protons at δ 1.45. These data account for the 2 : 2 dimethyl pyran ring in cycloheptazoline (ring D). The shift of the aldehydic band in the i.r. spectrum of cycloheptazoline (ν_{max}^{KBr} 1645 cm^{-1}) shows that the hydroxyl at 2 position is involved in the formation of the pyran ring. Evidently the signal for the hydroxyl group at 2 position (δ 9.82) is absent in the N.M.R. spectrum of the compound (II). These observations settle the positions of the formyl group, one hydroxyl and the $\gamma : \gamma$ dimethyl allyl chain in (I). The conclusions have been supported by the uv. data of heptazoline monoacetate, $C_{20}H_{19}NO_4$ (III), m.p. $159-60^\circ$ ($\lambda_{max}^{ethanol}$ 237, 275, 295 $m\mu$, $\log \epsilon$ 4.47, 4.60, 4.54 respectively; ν_{max}^{KBr} 1623 cm^{-1}) which shows that it has the effective heptaphylline⁷ (IV) chromophore ($\lambda_{max}^{ethanol}$ 234, 278, 298 and 346, $\log \epsilon$ 4.42, 4.53, 4.58 and 4.09). Since the aromatic proton at 5 position is both ortho and meta coupled, the second hydroxyl should occupy the position 8. This has been corroborated by the hydroxyl proton signal in the N.M.R. spectrum of cycloheptazoline (δ 11.05) which appears in more down field like that (δ 11.01) of 1-hydroxy carbazole (prepared by us starting from aniline and 2-formyl cyclohexanone⁸) and different from those of the hydroxyl groups at 3 (δ 10.65, in 6-methyl 3-hydroxy carbazole⁹) and at 2 positions (chelated *loc. cit.*). All these data lead to the assignment of the structure of heptazoline as (I)

The occurrence of heptazoline and heptaphylline in rutaceous plants provides biogenetic rationalisation of the pyranocarbazoles like girinimbine and murrayacine.

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